

IMPACT ANALYSIS OF COVID-19 ON HOTELS REVENUE IN JAYAPURA

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Abstract

In the midst of the rapid progress of the world today, a deadly disease that can spread very quickly has emerged, namely Covid-19. The beginning of the emergence of this disease was first reported in a city called Wuhan in China and was caused by the corona virus. The world seems to be shaken by a virus that is endemic and penetrates all aspects of life. This study aims to determine hotel revenues in the Abepura District of Jayapura City after the Covid-19 pandemic and the percentage of the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on the total hotel revenue. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative research method and descriptive quantitative research. The results of the study using a qualitative descriptive method showed that hotel revenues decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic due to the lack of visitors during 2020. Overall research results, using both qualitative descriptive and quantitative descriptive methods, concluded that the Covid-19 pandemic had a negative effect on income. Hotels, mainly from hotel room service revenues, restaurant service revenues, meeting room service revenues, rental service revenues and other facility services revenues.

Keywords: Impact of Covid-19; Hotel Revenue; Jayapura City

INTRODUCTION

Humans as social creatures who always gather (Putri & Wijaya, 2022) and interact with others and cannot live alone must now be forced to close themselves from the environment of society, neighbors, even the service environment is only because of the virus that can spread quickly, namely the corona virus which can also cause Covid-19 disease (Nasution & Hidayah, 2021). In December 2019, there was a group of (Levani, Prastya, & Mawaddatunnadila, 2021) cases of pneumonia of unknown cause that were linked to the Huanan seafood wholesale market. The market has thousands of stalls selling various animals such as fish, chickens, pheasants, bats, guinea pigs, venomous snakes, beehive deer and other wild animals. After the coronavirus was known to be the cause of this disease, suspicions were raised that new coronavirus was sourced from animals (Wahyudani, 2021). Most corona viruses circulate among animals (Safitri, 2021), but six species evolved and were able to infect humans, as seen in severe-acute respiratory syndrome. (SARS), Middle east respiratory syndrome (MERS) (Map, Arisadewo, Anwar, & Hasugian, 2021) and four other corona viruses that cause mild respiratory symptoms such as the flu (Noble, 2022).

The virus that so shook the world made all countries scattered in parts of the world worried about its spread, one of these countries, namely Indonesia. Concerns about the entry of the corona virus into Indonesia became a reality (Sofian & Lestarini, 2021). In mid-March 2020, the corona virus outbreak successfully entered (Lestari, 2021) Indonesia, after efforts to block the government over events in several surrounding countries (Pandiangan, Saragih, & Ancient,

2021). The corona virus outbreak or often called the Covid-19 pandemic originating from the Chinese city of Wuhan is rampant in countries spread throughout the world. Many countries are not prepared for this condition. Italy, Malaysia, Singapore have not escaped the spread of this new virus. Indonesia itself is affected by the indications coming from the arrival of Indonesians who have just returned from traveling from a country that has been infected with this virus before. Late awareness causes this virus to spread more and eventually cause casualties and panic in the midst of society.

The corona virus has affected the entire order of life of the country in general and especially people's lives. Social and cultural, political and economic aspects, and so on in people's lives once they feel the impact of the corona virus or often referred to as the Covid-19 pandemic. The aspect that was so hit during the Covid-19 pandemic was the economic aspect, both in terms of government and private or corporate. Many industries are not running according to the initial target. One of them is the hospitality industry, in the world of the hospitality industry every company wants to find a very large income, various ways are done to advance the company. Although there is competition between companies to maintain the survival of the company, but this is what basically spurs every company to provide better services in search of income. One of the most important elements of an income statement is revenue.

Revenue is the inflow obtained or cash inflow to be obtained that comes from the company's ongoing business activities. The revenue of the hospitality industry during the Covid-19 pandemic has decreased dramatically in all regions of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, this can be proven through research journals, print media, mass media and so on that there are many hotels that are forced to close because of no longer the arrival of guests and food and meeting businesses that are no longer filled. Indonesia is feeling the impact of the spread of the coronavirus or the Covid-19 pandemic. Currently, many policies have been carried out by the Central Government and Local Government to inhibit the spread of the coronavirus and also policies in the economic and welfare sectors of the community that greatly impact all lines of society without distinguishing the rank and class and strata of people's lives. The Indonesian Hotel and Restaurant Association noted that there are currently 1,642 hotels throughout Indonesia that have been forced to close due to the Covid-19 outbreak. With the closure of these hotels, the tourism industry has the potential to lose revenues of up to tens of trillions. Based on the records of the Indonesian Hotel and Restaurant Association, there are 1,642 hotels throughout Indonesia that have been forced to close because they are unable to survive the situation. The current Covid-19 pandemic, Papua Province in general and Jayapura City in particular Abepura District in this case the hospitality industry is experiencing changes that have a direct impact on the hotel admissions side. Based on the results of interviews between the author and several hotel employees consisting of Managers, Chief Accounting and Receptionists from eight hotels spread across Abepura District of Jayapura City, it can be concluded that hotel revenue before and after The Covid-19 pandemic has undergone a very drastic change. There are similarities in terms of revenue among the hospitality industry throughout Indonesia during the Covid-19 pandemic, the income of the hospitality industry before the Covid-19 outbreak is so good or it can be said that the hospitality industry is able to generate revenue in accordance with the targets that have been set and can

even exceed these targets. But after the Covid-19 outbreak, the hospitality industry's revenue is inversely proportional to before the Covid-19 pandemic. Hospitality industry revenue decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic to 50% of the company's target achievement.

If there is a very noticeable change in income like the case study above, it can be estimated that the hospitality industry whose capacity is like the jasmine class is threatened with lock hanging. When compared to the situation before the Covid-19 pandemic, the hospitality industry with various capacities provided provides comfort to visitors. Visitors who stay usually come from other areas in Tanah Papua to Jayapura City, especially Abepura District because Jayapura City is the Capital of Papua Province, then from outside Papua Province, some visitors include local and foreign tourists. Thus, the target revenue per day, per month and per year has been prepared and the facilities prepared become the attraction of visitors. The hospitality industry and its management are run by employees and hotel employees who are certainly competent and certainly professional. With the Covid-19 outbreak, the hospitality industry's revenue decreased so that some employees and hotel employees were dismissed both temporarily and permanently because hotel owners could not afford the salary costs of employees and their work. It is undeniable that the Covid-19 outbreak has affected all aspects of people's lives. The Papua Provincial Government's policy in dealing with the spread of the Covid-19 outbreak by closing all access in and out of communities spread throughout regencies and cities in Papua Province and self-isolation by doing activities from home.

The policy until now has entered one year of the entry of the corona virus or the Covid-19 pandemic continues to be considered by the Regional Government of Papua Province. Entering the celebration of Eid al-Fitr 1442 Hijri in 2021, the Government made an increase in preventing the spread of the coronavirus by closing strict access in and out and banning homecoming. Entering the second year for the Government, Private Parties and the public in general who are Muslim to refrain from going home to family, close and distant relatives to celebrate eid al-Fitr together. This certainly has a direct impact on the turnaround of the economic wheels that occur in an area, specifically the author wants to discuss the income of the hospitality industry in an area that has undergone such a significant change during the Covid-19 pandemic. The current situation of the Covid-19 pandemic has affected all aspects of government, private and general public life, this attracted the attention of the author to conduct a study entitled "Impact Analysis of Covid-19 on Hotels Revenue in Jayapura". This study aims to find out the revenue of hotels in Jayapura City after the Covid-19 pandemic and find out how much impact Covid-19 has on hotel revenue in Jayapura City.

RESEARCH METHODS

Design or research design is a framework used to carry out marketing research. Research design provides procedures to obtain the information needed to compile or solve problems in research, or it can be said that research design is the basis in conducting research. The research design used by the authors in this study is research using mixed methods or mix methods. The location of the study can be in a specific region or a specific institution in society. The research locations in this study are 8 (eight) hotels spread across jayapura city, especially in Abepura District,

including Cenderawasih Hotel, Kotaraja Hotel, Hotel 777, Gamalama Hotel, Grand Talent Hotel, Citihub Hotel, Bunga Youtefa Hotel and Bio Net Hotel. The time used by the author to conduct this research is carried out from the date of issuance of a research license or data collection by the administrative officer of the author's home campus faculty. In this study, the data obtained is in the form of primary data and secondary data with a research time of approximately 7 (seven) weeks, starting from April 12, 2021 - May 31, 2021 after the issuance of a research license and data retrieval by the campus faculty's administrative officer.

This research uses two variables, namely the free variable and the bound variable. Independent variables or variable X are variables that are seen as the cause of the emergence of bound variables that are suspected as a result. While the dependent variable or variable Y is a predicted variable (effect), which varies following the change of free variables. Generally, it is a condition that the author wants to express and explain. The following is a table of research variables.

Table 1: Research Variables

Independent Variables (X)	Indicator	Dependent Variables (AND)	Indicator
Impact of Covid-19	1. Increase in Revenue	Hotel Revenue	1. Hotel Room Service Sales
	2. Decrease in Revenue		2. Restaurant Service Sales
			3. Sales of Meeting Room Services
			4. Rental Service Sales
			5. Sales of Other Facilities Services

Source: Previous Research Journal (2021).

Data collection techniques in mix methods with a gradual mixed method strategy are strategies for authors to combine data found from one method with another. To analyze the data obtained in this study, the method used is a mixed method or mix methods because the author adjusts to the formulation of the problems raised in this study. Based on the 2 (two) problems raised in this thesis research, to discuss the first problem used qualitative descriptive analysis through interviews with hotel management located in Abepura District of Jayapura City. As for answering the second problem, quantitative descriptive analysis is used using income growth analysis using the growth formula from 2018 - 2020.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the description of the results of the above research, it is known that the average hotel revenue has decreased after the Covid-19 pandemic. Hotel Cenderawasih's revenue from the sale of hotel room services in 2018 amounted to Rp. 1,496,499,984 and increased in 2019 by Rp. 1,642,499,988 but during the Covid-19 pandemic hotel revenue decreased to Rp. 912,499,992. Apart from the sale of hotel room services, other revenues of Hotel Cenderawasih are sourced from the sale of rental services. Rental service sales revenue also decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic. Rental service sales revenue in 2018 amounted to Rp. 10,750,000, continued to increase in 2019 by Rp. 19,500,000. However, this income decreased due to the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 amounting to Rp. 7,000,000.

Kotaraja hotels also experienced a decrease in hotel room service sales revenue due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Hotel revenue in 2018 from the sale of hotel room services amounted to Rp. 547,500,000 and the revenue increased in 2019 by Rp. 657,000,000. After the pandemic in 2020, hotel revenue decreased by 50% more than the previous year's revenue of Rp. 219,000,000. The same thing happened to hotel 777 where the sales revenue of hotel room services decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic. Room service sales revenue in 2018 amounted to Rp. 1,167,999,996, in 2019 amounted to Rp. 1,021,999,992 and in 2020 there was a decrease in revenue to reach Rp. 291,999,996.

At Hotel Gamalama there are several indicators used to measure hotel revenue. These indicators include, the sale of room services, the sale of restaurant services, the sale of meeting room services and the sale of other facilities services. However, these four indicators showed a decrease in income during the Covid-19 pandemic. Room service sales revenue in 2018 amounted to Rp. 4,197,499,992, in 2019 amounted to Rp. 3,868,499,984 and the revenue decreased in 2020 by Rp. 1,934,499,996. The second indicator is the sale of restaurant services, in 2018 amounted to Rp. 152,000,000, in 2019 it amounted to Rp. 151,000,000 and decreased in 2020 by Rp. 11,000,000. The third indicator of meeting room service sales, in 2018 service sales amounted to Rp. 78,000,000, in 2019 amounted to Rp. 84,000,000 and the revenue decreased in 2020 by Rp. 10,000,000. The last indicator of Hotel Gamalama is the sale of other facilities services, service sales revenue in 2018 amounted to Rp. 143,000,000, in 2019 it amounted to Rp. 134,000,000 and decreased dramatically in 2020 to reach 50% more than Rp. 20,000,000.

Hotel Grand Talent is one of the star hotels that also experienced a decrease in revenue during the Covid-19 pandemic. The sales revenue of hotel room services in 2018 amounted to Rp. 6,204,999,984, in 2019 it was Rp. 5,876,499,984 and the revenue decreased in 2020 by Rp. 1,752,000,000. Apart from the sale of hotel room services, Grand Talent Hotel's revenue is also from the sale of restaurant services, in 2018 the revenue of restaurant service sales amounted to Rp. 860,000,000, in 2019 it was Rp. 951,000,000 and hotel revenue decreased in 2020 by Rp. 276,000,000.

The newly established Citihub Hotel in 2015 is one of the hotels that has also experienced the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic which has resulted in a decrease in hotel revenue. There are three indicators used by the author to measure the income of Citihub Hotels, including the sale of room services, the sale of restaurant services and the sale of meeting room services. The results of hotel room service sales showed that the revenue figures were stable in 2018 and 2019 amounting to Rp. 4,562,499,996 and in 2020 room service sales decreased by Rp. 1,669,499,988. The second indicator is that restaurant service sales show a decrease in revenue due to the pandemic, in 2018 revenues amounted to Rp. 970,000,000, in 2019 continued to increase to Rp. 995,000,000 and in 2020 the decline in restaurant service sales revenue amounted to Rp. 341,000,000. In addition to sales of hotel and restaurant room services, sales of meeting room services also decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2018, the sales revenue of meeting room services amounted to Rp. 76,000,000, in 2019 it was Rp. 73,000,000, and in 2020 it was Rp. 10,000,000.

The sales revenue of hotel room services that decreased during the Covid-19 pandemic was also experienced by Hotel Bunga Youtefa. Hotels that have only been operating for approximately 6 years have decreased revenue in 2020 when compared to previous years. Room service sales revenue in 2018 amounted to Rp. 1,642,500,000, in 2019 amounted to Rp. 1,533,000,000 and in 2020 hotel revenue decreased to Rp. 438,000,000. Unlike The Bunga Youtefa Hotel, Bio Net Hotel which has just been operating from the end of 2018 and the source of revenue only from the sale of hotel room services does not carry out the company's operational activities during the Covid-19 pandemic or converted the hotel building for other business activities. However, the sales revenue of room services in 2019 has a high nominal amount of Rp. 657,000,000 but the operational activities of the company or hotel still do not run throughout 2020.

HOW MUCH IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON HOTEL REVENUE

If you want to know the impact of Covid-19 on Hotel Revenue, then the author uses an analysis tool in the form of growth analysis using a growth formula whose results are outlined per hotel as follows.

Table 2: Cenderawasih Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	HK\$ 1,299.00	HK\$ 1,200.00	HK\$ 1,299.00	9.76%	-44.44%
2.	Rental Service Sales Revenue	Rp. 10.750.000	Rp. 19.500.000	Rp. 7.000.000	81.40%	-64.10%
Total Revenue		HK\$ 1,200.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,299.00	10.27%	-44.68%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

Based on the description of table 2 above, it is known that the growth of hotel revenue between 2018-2019 was 10.27% and between 2019-2020 it was -44.68%. Based on revenue indicators, the growth in hotel room service sales revenue between 2018-2019 was 9.76% and between 2019-2020 by -44.44% and the growth in rental service sales between 2018-2019 was 81.40% and between 2019-2020 by -64.10%. Revenue growth between 2019-2020 has a negative value or (-) shows that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on the growth rate of hotel revenue with a decrease in income that results directly in the reduction of labor both permanently and temporarily and other consequences such as restrictions on the use of other facilities such as restaurants, meeting rooms, and so on.

The above revenue growth rate shows a decrease in hotel revenue between 2019-2020. The above research has similarities in outline with the research journals Nuruddin, Putu Eka, Sri Pujiastuti, Ni Nyoman in 2020, and entitled Strategy to survive hotels in Bali during the Covid-19 pandemic. The results of this study showed that the impact of the pandemic resulted in hotel occupancy almost empty. The strategy carried out is almost the same, namely by dismissing employees and employees permanently or temporarily, limiting the use of hotel facilities, spending efficiency, selling non-room products online, to refusing to refund bookings by changing the visit schedule.

Table 3: Kotaraja Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	HK\$ 1,000.00	Hk\$ 1,000.00	Rp. 219,000,000	20.00%	-66.67%
	Total Revenue	HK\$ 1,000.00	Hk\$ 1,000.00	Rp. 219,000,000	20.00%	-66.67%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021).

Based on the description of table 3 above, it is known that the growth in hotel room service sales revenue between 2018-2019 was 20.00% and between 2019-2020 by -66.67%. Revenue growth between 2019-2020 has a negative value or (-) means that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on the rate of hotel revenue growth. Hotel management hopes that there will be regulations made by the government to help the smooth running of the hospitality business by easing the burden of hotel and restaurant taxes during the Covid-19 pandemic so that hospitality operations can continue to run during the Covid-19 pandemic. The decline in hotel revenue above has similarities with previous research, namely a researcher Lanang Diayudha in 2020, in a study entitled Hospitality Industry in Indonesia during the Covid-19 pandemic. The results of this descriptive analysis found that the hospitality industry needs more real relaxation from the government to save the industry.

Table 4: Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis 777

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	HK\$ 1,100,000.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,299.00	-12.50%	-71.43%
	Total Revenue	HK\$ 1,100,000.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,299.00	-12.50%	-71.43%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

Based on the description of table 4 above, it is known that the growth in hotel room service sales revenue between 2018-2019 was -12.50% and between 2019-2020 it was -71.43%. Revenue growth between 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 has a negative value or (-) the same as the previous two hotels, meaning that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on the growth rate of hotel revenue. This is supported by a research journal from a researcher from Makassar Syamsuddin in 2020, who researched the impact of Covid-19 on the target and realization of hotel and restaurant tax revenues in Makassar City. This research was motivated by the presence of Covid-19 which caused a decrease in economic activity which is suspected to have a negative impact on hotel and restaurant taxes in Makassar City. The results of this study showed that Covid-19 had a negative impact on the target and realization of hotel and restaurant tax revenues in Makassar City.

Based on the description of table 5 above, it is known that the growth of hotel revenue between 2018-2019 was -7.27% and between 2019-2020 it was -53.39%. Based on revenue indicators, the growth in hotel room service sales revenue between 2018-2019 amounted to -7.83% and between 2019-2020 by -50.00%, the growth in restaurant service sales revenue between 2018-2019 by -0.66% and between 2019-2020 by -92.72%, and the growth in meeting room service

sales revenue between 2018-2019 amounted to 7.69% and between 2019-2020 amounted to -88.10% and the growth in sales revenue of other facilities services between 2018-2019 by 2019.10% and the growth in sales revenue of other facilities between 2019. in 2018-2019 by -6.29% and between 2019-2020 by -85.07%. The rate of revenue growth between 2019-2020 has a negative value or (-) indicates that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on hotel revenue growth with a decrease in revenue from the years before the pandemic.

Table 5: Gamalama Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	Rp. 4.197.499.992	HK\$ 1,299.00	HK\$ 1,200.00	-7.83%	-50.00%
2.	Restaurant Services Sales Revenue	Rp. 152.000.000	Rp. 151.000.000	Rp. 11.000.000	-0.66%	-92.72%
3.	Meeting Room Service Sales Revenue	Rp. 78.000.000	Rp. 84.000.000	Rp. 10.000.000	7.69%	-88.10%
4.	Revenue for Sales of Other Facilities Services	Rp. 143.000.000	Rp. 134.000.000	Rp. 20.000.000	-6.29%	-85.07%
Total Revenue		HK\$ 1,200.00	HK\$ 1,200.00	HK\$ 1,299,000.00	-7.27%	-53.39%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021).

Based on table 5 above, the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic has an average impact on all business sectors, one of which is the hospitality industry which is the largest fundraiser to the tourism sector through its operational activities. The Covid-19 pandemic caused not only the hospitality industry to suffer losses but the tourism sector also felt the loss supported by the research journal Henri Ananta, Ahmad Rizkon, Ajeng Swastika Sari, M. Abul Karim, Lukman Dwi Prastiyanto, Sri Mularsih in 2020, entitled Analysis of the impact of Covid-19 on the tourism sector of Sikembang Park Blado District, Batang Regency. The tourism sector is one of the contributing sectors to regional income. But since Covid-19, the revenue budget from the tourism sector has fallen sharply. This is done in anticipation of the transmission of Covid-19. Various efforts have been made by the manager of Sikembang Park so that tourists can still travel but in accordance with health protocols set by the government. These efforts include checking body temperature, wearing masks, maintaining distance and washing hands.

Table 6: Grand Talent Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	HK\$ 1,200.00	HK\$ 1,299.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	-5.29%	-70.19%
2.	Restaurant Services Sales Revenue	Rp. 860.000.000	Rp. 951.000.000	Rp. 276.000.000	10.58%	-70.98%
Total Revenue		HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,200.00	Hk\$ 1,000.00	-3.36%	-70.30%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

Based on the description of table 6 above, it is known that the growth of hotel revenue between 2018-2019 was -3.36% and between 2019-2020 it was -70.30%. Based on revenue indicators, the growth in hotel room service sales revenue between 2018-2019 was -5.29% and between 2019-2020 by -70.19%, and the growth in restaurant service sales revenue between 2018-2019 was 10.58% and between 2019-2020 by -70.98%. Revenue growth between 2019-2020 has a

negative value or (-) shows that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on the growth rate of hotel revenue with a decrease in revenue from the years before the pandemic and resulting in permanent or temporary dismissal of employees and employees.

With the decline in revenue through the calculation of revenue growth above, it directly resulted in a reduction in hotel employees and employees during the Covid-19 pandemic. This shows the similarity of the results of the study with the research journal of a researcher named Silpa Hanoatubun in 2020, with the title of research on the impact of Covid-19 on the Indonesian economy. The results of this study show the impact of Covid-19 on the Indonesian economy, among others, there are stops and reductions in labor in almost all sectors of government and private businesses that are temporary and permanent, there are difficulties in finding jobs, so this has a direct impact on the difficulty of meeting daily needs.

Table 7: Citi hub Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	HK\$ 1,299.00	HK\$ 1,299.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	0.00%	-63.41%
2.	Restaurant Services Sales Revenue	Rp.970.000.000	Rp. 995.000.000	Rp. 341.000.000	2.58%	-65.73%
3.	Meeting Room Service Sales Revenue	Rp.76.000.000	Rp.73.000.000	Rp.10.000.000	-3.95%	-86.30%
Total Revenue		HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,200,000.00	0.39%	-64.12%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

The revenue growth in table 7 above seen between 2019-2020 has a negative value or (-) shows that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on the rate of hotel revenue growth with a decrease in revenue from the years before the pandemic and resulting in permanent or temporary dismissal of employees and employees.

The decrease in revenue above is due to the loneliness of hotel room visitors during the pandemic and even restaurant and meeting room visitors, the current Covid-19 pandemic situation has affected all aspects of community business both on a small, medium to large business scale. This research has similarities with a research journal entitled Analysis of the Impact of Covid-19 on the Income of MSMEs (Small and Medium Micro Enterprises) Blado Village, Batang Regency in 2020 which was studied by Alvia Pratiwi Putri, Devi Novita Sari, Henry Ananta, Izzatul Marifah, Khamami and Lalang Hadi Husodo. The results of this study show the impact caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, including the level of people's purchasing power decreased and the market situation became quiet.

Table 8: Youtefa Flower Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	Hk\$ 1,000.00	-6.67%	-71.43%
Total Revenue		HK\$ 1,000.00	HK\$ 1,000.00	Hk\$ 1,000.00	-6.67%	-71.43%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

Based on the description of table 8 above, it is known that the growth in hotel room service sales revenue between 2018-2019 was -6.67% and between 2019-2020 it was -71.43%. The rate of revenue growth between 2019-2020 has a negative value or (-) means that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on the growth rate of hotel revenue. Hotel management hopes that there will be regulations made by the government to help the smooth running of the hospitality business by easing the burden of hotel and restaurant taxes during the Covid-19 pandemic so that hospitality operations can continue to run during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Table 8 of the above income growth shows that there is a similarity in the results of research, namely a decrease in the income side caused by the Covid-19 pandemic with the previous research of researcher Eka Budiyanti in 2020, which examined the impact of Covid-19 on the Indonesian trade and tourism sector. The results showed that there was a decline in the Chinese economy which had an impact on the decline of the Indonesian economy, especially in the trade and tourism sectors. The government needs to find alternative policies and strategies to boost the domestic economy without having to rely on imports of goods from China and also seek a share of exports to countries other than China. The government also needs to be observant to see opportunities in the tourism sector to attract tourists from other countries to visit Indonesia and increase domestic tourists.

Table 9: Bio Net Hotel Revenue Growth Analysis

No	Information	Growth Realization			Growth	
		Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2018/ 2019	Year 2019/2020
1.	Hotel Room Service Sales Revenue	-	Hk\$ 1,000.00	-	-	-100.00%
	Total Revenue	-	Hk\$ 1,000.00	-	-	-100.00%

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021).

Revenue growth between 2019-2020 has a negative value indicating that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on hotel revenue growth resulting in a temporary switch or conversion of the hotel business into other business activities.

The above research when associated with a research journal entitled Analysis of the Influence of Covid-19 on the Economy in the Tourism Sector in Bawang District, Batang Regency which was studied by Afik Kushendrawan, Diana Naela, Henry Ananta, Nelly Alya and Widatul in 2020 there are similarities from the two results of this study. The results showed that the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on Bio Net Hotel revenue by 100% and the Covid-19 pandemic had a significant effect on the economy and tourism sector in Bawang District, Batang Regency.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and discussion that have been outlined, the author concluded that the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative impact on hotel revenue. Both Hotel Cenderawasih, Hotel Kotaraja, Hotel 777, Hotel Gamalama, Hotel Grand Talent, Hotel Citi hub, Hotel Bunga Youtefa and Hotel Bio Net. The eight hotels experienced a decrease in sales revenue for hotel room services, restaurant services, meeting room services, rental services and other facility

services and there were restrictions on the sale of hotel services such as the sale of hotel services, the sale of restaurant services, the sale of meeting room services, the sale of rental services and the sale of other facilities services during the pandemic which resulted in a temporary and permanent reduction in labor.

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